

List of EOVs/EBVs for assessing cumulative effects identified

Milestone 5.4

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1. GES4SEAS Project Summary

Human activities at sea (e.g., maritime transport, extraction of living and non-living resources, etc.) and in coastal areas (e.g., agriculture, leisure and recreation, etc.) have expanded considerably, leading to an increased level of pressures and subsequent degradation of ocean health and, ultimately, human health. Single and cumulative impacts of these activities are likely to increase, driven by human demands and enhanced by climate change.

Human activities evolve following socio-economic drivers leading to pressures, which often are studied in isolation from each other even though their impacts on marine ecosystems can interact, making the effects cumulative (e.g., synergistic, antagonistic or a combination). Knowledge on these interactions and their cumulative effects in the marine environment has increased in recent years, but huge challenges still remain to be solved. Thus, there is little predictability with which to inform decision-making processes, especially on ecological tipping points, which, if exceeded, could lead to a point of no-return for the system. In this context, an ecosystem-based management (EBM) approach to the management of human activities at sea and on land should ensure that the combined pressure of such activities is kept within levels compatible with the achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) (requirements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive – MSFD), against a background of climate change. This means that the capacity of marine and coastal ecosystems to respond to human-induced changes is not compromised, enabling the sustainable use of marine goods and services by present and future generations.

Thus, the main objective of GES4SEAS is to inform and guide marine governance in minimizing human pressures and their impacts on marine biodiversity and ecosystem functioning, while maintaining the sustainable delivery of ecosystem services. This will be achieved through developing an innovative and flexible toolbox, tested, validated, demonstrated and upscaled, in the context of adaptive EBM approach. The toolbox will allow competent authorities to assess and predict the effect of multiple stressors (including climate change) and pressures from human activities, at the national, sub-regional, regional and European level. Ultimately, this will ensure they achieve GES, and support different policies at national, European and global levels (e.g., Birds and Habitats Directives (BHD), Biodiversity Strategy 2030, United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)).

Stakeholders and the key competent authorities (including national, regional and European levels) are integrated in a Practitioner Advisory Board (PAB) to co-create and validate the toolbox and the EBM approach. This will result on a real problem-solving approach with iterative and incremental development steps.

GES4SEAS will also rely on existing multi-actor networks to involve and engage with stakeholders. This multi-actor approach will ensure that the research and deliverables are relevant to marine managers all around the world. Lastly, it is important to highlight that the toolbox will be tested and demonstrated at 11 Learning Sites (LSs) covering all European regional seas (and also overseas), and environments. Thus, it is expected that GES4SEAS will achieve Technological and Societal Readiness Levels 6. This will be achieved by the participation of 20 partners, covering the four European regional seas and Canada.

It is expected that GES4SEAS will:

- Operationalize integrative and holistic solutions for EBM, based upon a software toolbox for analysing, assessing and mapping cumulative pressures, GES and ecosystem services.
- Provide evidence (and training) to key stakeholders of the benefits of using the toolbox that will be developed in GES4SEAS for assessing the environmental status of marine waters and the ecosystem services considering the effects of multiple pressures so opt for using it.
- Ensure the EBM approach and guidelines for the management of Invasive Alien Species (IAS), harmful algal blooms (HABs) and jellyfish, the approach for monitoring top predators are used by end-users.
- Investigate, using models, the best ways to obtain thresholds of GES/non-GES status and tipping points (system breaking points).
- Reach and engage a wider society, and specifically young people and educators, on key messages stemming from this project, so GES4SEAS contributes to societal ocean literacy and responsible behaviours.

2. Introduction

Milestone 5.4 identifies a list of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) that can support MSFD reporting and provide a monitoring basis for future work on cumulative pressures in European seas. This milestone report identifies Essential Variables (EVs), used here as an umbrella term for EOVs and EBVs, that are linked to MSFD criteria and to the monitoring of ecosystem functions. These EVs can therefore help prioritize monitoring variables that address known gaps in national monitoring reporting and support future cumulative-effects assessment. This milestone is aligned with Article 8(1) of the MSFD, which requires “*Member States to assess the predominant pressures and impacts on marine waters, including the qualitative and quantitative mix of pressures, discernible trends, and their cumulative and synergistic effects*” while evaluating the potential of monitoring frameworks on informing policy criteria.

Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA) requires robust and comparable information on ecosystem state, pressures, impacts and ecosystem functioning. Essential Variables (are promoted and implemented with the goal to harmonise biodiversity monitoring and ocean observations across species, habitats, communities and ecosystem processes, while also addressing known gaps in European biodiversity monitoring (Santana et al., 2025; Kissling et al., 2026, Martín-Míguez et al., 2026).

3. Methods

The evaluation of EVs was implemented through two elicitation expert exercises, developed to assess how EOVs and EBVs can support MSFD reporting and provide a monitoring basis for future work on cumulative pressures. The first exercise linked EVs to MSFD criteria to identify variables informative for Good Environmental Status assessment. The second exercise linked EVs to ecosystem functions to identify variables relevant for monitoring ecosystem processes that are not always directly represented in MSFD criteria. Together, both exercises were used to classify EV linkages according to relevance, confidence and agreement, and to identify monitoring priorities and remaining evidence gaps.

3.1 Linking Essential Variables to MSFD criteria

A series of surveys was designed to collect information from experts to identify which EOVs and EBVs are informative for MSFD criteria and Good Environmental Status assessment. The survey was extended within the GES4SEAS consortium and distributed to several experts, including partner institutions and participants from the JRC/ACTEON “*Future of Marine Biodiversity Monitoring*” workshop. Building on the 62 responses to the EV-MSFD survey, we aggregated the results at the level of each EV to MSFD-criterion pair.

For each EV × MSFD-criterion pair, respondents provided a linkage score and an overall confidence rating on a 0-5 scale. We calculated two single metrics to evaluate the relevance of the linkages. The first metric was based on an unweighted mean linkage score, as the simple average of all available responses. The second metric was a weighted mean linkage score, which was based on a confidence-weighted mean linkage score, where responses from participants with higher confidence contributed more strongly to the average. Confidence values by respondents were rescaled between 0 and 1 and used as weights only when both a linkage score and a confidence rating were available

To assess the robustness of each linkage, the share of responses that included confidence information and the effective sample size was calculated. The effective sample size indicates how much information is effectively contributing to the weighted score. When confidence weights were similar across respondents, the effective sample size remained close to the number of confidence-rated answers. When only a few high-confidence responses dominated the result, the effective sample size was smaller, indicating higher uncertainty.

Agreement between respondents was assessed using a confidence-weighted dispersion by means of the standard deviation (SD). Low dispersion indicates that respondents gave similar scores and

therefore that the linkage is consistent. High dispersion indicates greater disagreement and therefore a more contested linkage. EV × MSFD pairs with few scored responses, few confidence-rated responses or low effective sample size were labelled as “*Limited data*”.

Each EV × MSFD-criterion pair was classified according to its confidence-weighted mean score and its level of agreement into 5 categories (Figure 2): “*Highly informative and consistent*” linkages (HIC), “*Highly informative but contested*” linkages (HICc), “*Not informative and consistent*” linkages (NIC), “*Not Informative but contested*” linkages (NICc). “*Highly informative*” linkages were used to identify EVs that are most directly useful for MSFD reporting, while “*Not informative but contested*” (NICc) and Limited data linkages are reported as candidate requiring further expert review.

To evaluate how EVs relate to current MSFD implementation, the variables identified as *Highly Informative and Consistent* (HIC) and *Highly Informative but Contested* (HIC-contested) were compared against the parameters and units reported in the 2018 WISE-Marine Good Environmental Status (GES) assessments

3.2 Linking Essential Variables to ecosystem function monitoring

To complement the MSFD criterion mapping, expert input was used to identify EVs that are relevant for monitoring ecosystem functions. This step was included because ecosystem functions are monitored in research contexts, but are not explicitly reported or harmonised in national monitoring programmes. Ecosystem-based management requires information on how human activities affect not only ecosystem state, but also the functions that support ecosystem services. The workshop took place during the GES4SEAS 3rd annual meeting (2025) and included project partner institutions and members of the JRC. This step is relevant because MSFD criteria mostly evaluate ecosystem components, pressures and state indicators, while ecosystem functions are not always directly represented in MSFD reporting, with the exception of food-web components assessed under Descriptor 4. Examples of ecosystem functions considered here include primary production, nutrient cycling, habitat provision, nursery function, trophic regulation, biological mediation and carbon sequestration.

The workshop was developed in expert groups, where each group provided feedback using scoring matrices that linked EOVs and EBVs to ecosystem functions. Ecosystem-function terminology and classification followed that of the frameworks linking marine ecosystem components, processes and functions by Armoškaitė et al (2020) and implemented in the EU project AQUACROSS Nogueira et al. (2016). Linkages were scored using a 0–5 Likert scale, following the same scoring used for linking EVs

to MSFD criteria (*see previous section*). Linkages not scored or “NA” were treated as no answer and kept distinct from scores of 0, while empty pair linkages are reported as not prioritised or not evaluated, consistent with the workshop aim of identifying the strongest linkages rather than scoring every possible pair. When expert groups did not agree on a single score, multiple scores were treated as unresolved within-group disagreement. These cases were not interpreted as invalid or uninformative scores, but as linkages whose relevance may be context-dependent. This means that the EV may still be relevant for monitoring an ecosystem function, but the strength of the linkage may depend on the species, habitat, ecosystem type, spatial context, or monitoring method considered. When expert groups did not agree on a single score, multiple scores were treated as unresolved within-group disagreement. The median was used only as a representative value for descriptive summaries.

EV-Ecosystem Function (EF) linkages were classified using two attributes: relevance strength and cross-group support. Relevance was described using the median group score. Support was described using the number of groups scoring the linkage and the agreement between groups. Linkages were then assigned to evidence classes: A) for strongly supported linkages, B) for high-relevance linkages identified by a single group, C) for moderate but consistent linkages, D) for contested or uncertain linkages and E) for linkages not prioritised or not evaluated. This classification allowed us to retain all those linkages relevant to evaluate ecosystem function from multiple- or single-group experts with higher confidence to linkages supported by multiple groups.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Coverage of MSFD criteria by Essential Variables

The expert-based scoring evaluated 2,200 pairwise combinations between EVs and MSFD criteria and identified a total of 187 EV-criterion linkages, of which 137 (73%) were classified as direct, 28 (15%) as indirect, and 22 (12%) as mixed. From the 55 EVs evaluated, 14 Essential variables are considered *Highly informative* EVs (HIC and HICc) for four Descriptors (D1-Biodiversity, D3-Commercial Species, D4-Food Webs and D6-Sea Floor Integrity) across 14 criteria, 13 on State of Species and Ecosystems and one on monitoring Pressures (Physical disturbance to the seabed) (Figure 1). Overall, 15 unique EVs had at least one *highly informative linkage* (HIC or HICc) to MSFD criteria (Table 1). These highly informative EVs were mostly associated with species or habitat state, including abundance, distribution, cover, composition and habitat condition.

Figure 1. Confidence sensitivity of EV x MSFD linkage scores. Each point represents one EV x MSFD-criterion pair for each of the descriptors. The y-axis shows the confidence-weighted mean score, computed using only responses with an expert confidence rating. The x-axis shows the dispersion, measured as the standard deviation for the scoring from the experts. Dot colour encodes the agreement classification, point size scales with the effective sample size (n_{eff}), and transparency reflects the share of responses that include a confidence rating. Descriptor 8 and 9 were evaluated in the same survey and collated into the Marine Litter facet.

A total of 137 direct linkages (73 HIC and 64 HICc) with 7 EVs accounting for over 80% of direct linkages to MSFD criteria such as: Hard coral cover and composition (EOV, $n=20$), Seagrass cover and composition (EOV, $n=20$), Invertebrate abundance and distribution (*pilot) (EOV, $n=18$), Fish abundance and distribution (EOV, $n=16$), Species abundances (EBV, $n=14$), Macroalgal canopy cover and composition (EOV, $n=12$), Species distributions (EBV, $n=12$). These EBVs and EOVs partly overlap in their contribution to MSFD criteria, as both frameworks capture key aspects of the state of

ecosystem components such as abundance, distribution, and composition. The distinction between them is therefore not in the information provided, but in how variables are framed: EOVs often refer to more specific observation-based variables on specific Species and Habitats, whereas EBVs tend to represent more generalised variables that can be applied across different species.

Table 1. Essential Variables classified as highly informative for Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) criteria. HIC = highly informative and consistent; HICc = highly informative but contested. “Total links” refers to the number of Essential Variables (EV)-criterion records classified as HIC or HICc. EBV: Essential Biodiversity Variables; EOVS: Essential Ocean Variables.

Framework	Essential Variable	HIC	HICc	MSFD Descriptors	MSFD Criteria linked *
EBV	Species distributions	3	12	4	14
EBV	Species abundances	7	7	4	13
EOV	Fish abundance and distribution	3	6	3	9
EOV	Invertebrate abundance and distribution (*pilot)	4	4	2	7
EOV	Seagrass cover and composition	3	5	2	7
EOV	Hard coral cover and composition	2	5	2	6
EOV	Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	3	3	2	5
EOV	Marine turtles, birds, mammals abundance and distribution	3	3	2	6
EBV	Community abundance	2	4	2	6
EOV	Phytoplankton biomass and diversity	2	4	3	6
EOV	Zooplankton biomass and diversity	1	3	2	4
EBV	Genetic diversity	1	1	1	2
EOV	Mangrove cover and composition	1	1	1	2
EBV	Interaction diversity	0	2	1	2
EBV	Taxonomic/phylogenetic diversity	0	1	1	1

* Link counts by MSFD criterion may differ from total HIC/HICc counts because the same EV could be linked to the same criterion through more than one linkage type, such as direct or indirect. Therefore, total HIC/HICc records can be higher than the number of unique MSFD criteria covered.

While most linkages scored by experts are considered directly informative for MSFD state criteria, a substantial proportion (27%) of EVs are considered to indirectly inform MSFD or depend on monitoring context-dependent. These non-direct linkages suggest that EVs would require further evaluation and additional harmonization or integration with other variables to fully support MSFD assessments. This alignment primarily reflects conceptual consistency rather than operational equivalence, as our evaluation did not assess MSFD reporting thresholds for GES/non-GES classification. The results also show important limitations in the current expert base, linkages for four descriptors, D2 Non-indigenous species, D4 Food Webs, D5 Eutrophication and D8/D9 Contamination, included cases with limited data and low confidence. In addition, no expert scoring was available for D7 Hydrographical Conditions, D10 Marine Litter and D11 Underwater Sound. This indicates that the current linkage map

is strongest for state-related descriptors and less complete for descriptors related to pressures and impacts.

Parameters extracted from WISE-Marine were grouped by descriptor and criterion. In this section, “EVs” refer to the broader Essential Variables used to structure monitoring, while “parameters” refer to the specific measurements or metrics reported by Member States in WISE-Marine to assess MSFD criteria. These parameters can use different names, units or metrics while still describing the same type of information captured by an EV. For example, an EV related to abundance may correspond to MSFD-reported parameters such as counts, density, or number of individuals per unit area. The units and measurement types associated with both EVs and MSFD-reported parameters were therefore grouped into broader parameter dimensions, meaning parameters that report similar information even when they are measured with different metrics or units. These parameter dimensions are defined as abundance, distribution/extent, biomass, diversity/composition, habitat condition, and demography/size structure.

This was necessary because current MSFD reporting remains affected by inconsistent terminology, methodological differences and variation in reported units across criteria and Member States (Nikolaou et al., 2025). Once grouped into these broader dimensions, current MSFD state reporting shows that several dimensions are used across more than one descriptor, especially demography/size structure, abundance, distribution/extent and biomass (Figure 2a). Expert-supported EVs (HIC and HICc), show a similar pattern, mainly covering: abundance, extent/distribution, diversity/composition and habitat condition (Figure 2b-c). However, some differences are clear for the variable/indicator/parameter habitat condition as it is currently reported across several descriptors, but expert-supported EVs mainly link it to D1 Biodiversity and D6 Seafloor integrity; and abundance is currently used for D4 Food webs, while expert EV linkages associate it more strongly with D1, D3 and D6. This shows that EVs can support harmonised MSFD state monitoring, but some descriptor-specific assessments, especially D4 Food webs, require combining abundance with other dimensions such as biomass, diversity/composition or interaction networks.

Figure 2. Overlap of parameter dimensions used in MSFD state reporting and expert-supported EV linkages. Stacked barplots show the number of MSFD criteria associated with each parameter dimension, separated by MSFD descriptor. a) Parameter dimensions currently used in WISE-MARINE reporting for MSFD state criteria as reported by members state (WISE-MARINE dashboard for the 2018 Reporting cycle). b) Parameter dimensions represented by highly informative and consistent EV-criterion linkages (HIC). c) Parameter dimensions represented by highly informative but contested EV-criterion linkages (HIC-contested). Bar colours indicate MSFD descriptors: D1 Biodiversity, D3 Commercial fish, D4 Food webs and D6 Seafloor integrity.

4.2. Links between Essential Variables and ecosystem function monitoring.

Across the 55 EVs and 20 ecosystem functions, the elicitation matrix contained 1,100 possible EV–function pairs. Of these, 554 pairs (50.4%) received at least one numeric score from the groups, while 546 pairs (49.6%) were left unscored (i.e., not prioritised/not evaluated in the workshop context). The workshop results were used to classify EV–function linkages according to relevance and support. Strongly supported linkages were those with high relevance, supported by at least two groups, and having low between-group variation. High single-group highlights were retained where one expert group identified a highly relevant linkage (Figure 3). Applying the classification classes, 93 pairs (8.5%

of all pairs; 16.8% of scored pairs) were identified as monitoring-relevant linkages in classes A-C (33 A, 30 B, 30 C). At the EV level, 17 EVs (30.9%) received no scores at all (8 EBVs and 9 EOVs), and were therefore not included in further analysis; the unevaluated EBVs were mostly in Species Traits & Functional Diversity, while the unevaluated EOVs were predominantly biogeochemistry/nutrient state variables (e.g., dissolved organic carbon, nutrients, oxygen). Only two EVs had very limited coverage (scored only twice across the full matrix): Ecosystem disturbances (EBV) and Ocean sound (EOV).

Figure 3. Heatmap of median expert-elicited relevance scores (0–5) linking Essential Variables (EVs; y-axis) to ecosystem functions (EF; x-axis). EV labels are colour-coded by framework (EBV vs EOV). EV x EF pairs are coloured by the group-median Likert score and those EVs scored as highly relevant are outlined by red outlines: A strongly supported linkages (*), B high-relevance linkages identified by a single group (**), and C moderate but consistent linkages (***). EVs scores not classified in either relevance class are shown with reduced opacity to emphasise the shortlisted linkages.

Ecosystem functions related to the presence of essential habitats contained the largest set of monitoring-relevant linkages, with 40 linkages out of 275 possible pairs (14.5%) categorized as either A, B or C. Within this group, Habitat provision and Nursery function each had 12 A-C links, together

accounting for 24 of 40 habitat-related links (60%), while Refugia had the fewest (4 links). Productivity functions showed 14 A-C links out of 110 pairs (12.7%), involving 10 EVs, with most links associated with Secondary production (9) rather than Primary production (5). Biogeochemical cycles showed 16 A-C links out of 330 pairs (4.8%), and Nutrient production & recycling showed 10 A-C links out of 110 pairs (9.1%). In the “other ecosystem functions” group, 13 A-C links were identified across five functions, driven largely by biological control (7 links); Filtration had no A-C links in this elicitation output.

The top EVs contributing to monitoring-relevant evidence included both EOVs and EBVs (Table 2). Seagrass cover and composition showed the highest number of strongly supported linkages, followed by phytoplankton biomass and diversity, species abundances, species distributions, ecosystem distribution, ecosystem vertical profile, mangrove cover and composition, macroalgal canopy cover and composition, ecosystem phenology, and microbe biomass and diversity.

Table 2. Top Essential Variables (EVs) relevant for monitoring Ecosystem function (relevance classification A to C) and their linkages class counts. EBV: Essential Biodiversity Variables; EOVS: Essential Ocean Variables.

Framework	Essential Variable	A	B	C	D	Scored links
EOV	Seagrass cover and composition	11	0	2	3	20
EOV	Phytoplankton biomass and diversity	4	0	2	5	20
EBV	Species abundances	3	0	0	0	20
EBV	Species distributions	3	0	0	0	20
EBV	Ecosystem distribution	2	0	9	1	20
EBV	Ecosystem vertical profile	2	0	9	1	19
EOV	Mangrove cover and composition	2	2	0	0	13
EOV	Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	2	1	0	0	20
EBV	Ecosystem phenology	1	5	0	0	20
EOV	Microbe biomass and diversity (*pilot)	1	2	2	0	19

These EVs are relevant because they connect observable monitoring variables to ecosystem functions such as primary production, habitat provision, trophic structure, biomass accumulation, community regulation and nutrient cycling. For example, seagrass cover and composition, macroalgal canopy cover and ecosystem distribution are linked to habitat provision and structural functions, while phytoplankton biomass and diversity and microbe biomass and diversity are linked to productivity, nutrient cycling and lower trophic-level processes. Species abundances and species distributions provide information on changes in populations and communities that can indicate functional change across multiple MSFD descriptors.

The results therefore show that EVs can complement MSFD criteria by providing monitoring variables that are closer to ecosystem functioning. This is important for cumulative-effects assessment because cumulative effects are not only expressed as changes in individual criteria, but also through changes in the capacity of ecosystems to maintain functions and services.

4.3. Relevance for cumulative-effects assessment

This Milestone identifies a priority list of EVs that are highly consistent with MSFD state criteria and/or strongly linked to ecosystem function monitoring. These EVs can be used as the monitoring basis for future cumulative-effects assessment because they provide information on the ecosystem components and processes that are likely to respond to multiple pressures.

This approach is aligned with the MSFD Article 8 requirement to assess predominant pressures and impacts, including cumulative and synergistic effects. EVs can support this requirement by providing harmonised variables that describe biodiversity state, ecosystem structure and ecosystem functioning. In this way, the EV list can help identify which monitoring variables should be prioritised when evaluating whether multiple pressures are affecting the same species groups, habitats, communities or functions.

The recommended list should therefore be interpreted as a monitoring-priority list for cumulative-effects assessment, not as a cumulative-effects assessment itself. The strongest priorities are those EVs that meet two conditions: they are highly informative and consistent for MSFD criteria, and they are also relevant for ecosystem function monitoring. EVs meeting both conditions are particularly useful because they can link policy reporting under the MSFD with ecological interpretation of how ecosystems respond to cumulative pressures.

5. Conclusion

This Milestone identifies a focused list of Essential Ocean Variables and Essential Biodiversity Variables that can support MSFD monitoring priorities. The EV -> MSFD results shows that several EVs are conceptually aligned with MSFD criteria, especially those describing the state of species and habitats, such as abundance, distribution, biomass, habitat extent, composition and habitat condition. These variables are already partly represented in MSFD reporting, although often through inconsistent terminology and units. As EV frameworks are increasingly promoted as standardised and harmonised monitoring approaches, they can help organise existing observations into more consistent reporting dimensions for MSFD implementation.

The ecosystem function results complement the MSFD mapping by identifying EVs that can support future monitoring of ecosystem functions. This is relevant because ecosystem functions are not consistently required, reported or harmonised in national monitoring programmes, despite being central to ecosystem-based management and to the maintenance of ecosystem services. EVs such as seagrass cover and composition, phytoplankton biomass and diversity, species abundances, species distributions, ecosystem distribution, ecosystem vertical profile and macroalgal canopy cover and composition were especially relevant for linking ecosystem state to ecosystem-function monitoring.

Important limitations remain. The current linkage map is strongest for state-related descriptors, while pressure and impact criteria have lower coverage. Several EOVs that could help evaluate pressures, impacts and climate-related changes were not strongly highlighted in the current expert-based scoring, partly reflecting the expert composition and the current focus of the assessment. In addition, some descriptors had limited data, low confidence or no scoring, showing that broader expert input is needed to refine the overlap between EVs and MSFD reporting needs. The current results should therefore be interpreted as a first expert-based prioritisation, not as a final operational framework.

Together, these results support the use of EVs as a bridge between monitoring data and MSFD criteria. EVs frameworks have the potential to harmonized transnational monitoring by reducing redundant or inconsistent reporting across descriptors. Comparable monitoring data are needed to evaluate the impact of multiple pressures on ecosystem components and functions. While cumulative effects are not assessed in this Milestone, the proposed EV list identifies provides a first monitoring-priority basis for future implementation of Article 8(1) of the MSFD in relation to cumulative and synergistic effects.

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7. Glossary

Term	Abbreviation	Definition
Cumulative effects	CE	Combined effects of multiple pressures acting together on marine ecosystems.
Essential Biodiversity Variable	EBV	A Framework of minimum set of variables needed to monitor biodiversity change. EBVs cover biodiversity from genes to ecosystems, including genetic composition, species populations, species traits, community composition, ecosystem function and ecosystem structure. EBVs are intended to harmonise biodiversity monitoring and support policy reporting across realms and countries (Kissling et al., 2026).
Essential Ocean Variable	EOV	A core ocean variable used to monitor physical, biogeochemical, biological or ecosystem properties of the ocean
Essential Variables	EVs	General term used in this report to refer jointly to EOVs and EBVs.
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	MSFD	
Good Environmental Status	GES	The environmental status of marine waters where ecosystems are clean, healthy, productive and ecologically diverse, while allowing sustainable use by current and future generations.
MSFD descriptor		One of the 11 qualitative descriptors used by the MSFD to assess marine environmental status, such as biodiversity, non-indigenous species, commercial fish, food webs, eutrophication, seafloor integrity, contaminants, marine litter and underwater noise.
MSFD criteria		A technical assessment component within an MSFD descriptor. Criteria are used to determine whether Good Environmental Status is achieved for specific ecosystem elements, pressures or impacts.
State criteria		MSFD Criteria describing the condition of an ecosystem component, such as species abundance, habitat extent, community composition or ecosystem condition.
Pressure criteria		MSFD criteria describing a pressure acting on the marine environment, such as nutrient enrichment, physical disturbance, contaminants, litter or underwater noise.
Impact criteria		MSFD criterion describing the ecological effect of a pressure on ecosystem components or processes.
Ecosystem function	EF	A precise effect of a given constraint on the ecosystem flow of matter and energy performed by a given item of biodiversity, within a closure of constraints. Ecosystem

		functions include decomposition, production, nutrient cycling, and fluxes of nutrients and energy (AQUACROSS project)
Linkage score		Expert-assigned score describing how relevant an EV is for an MSFD criterion or ecosystem function. In the analyses, scores were given on a 0–5 scale.
Confidence score		Expert-assigned score describing how confident the respondent was in their assessment of an EV linkage.
Effective sample size (Neff)		Measure of how much information contributes to a confidence-weighted score. If only a few high-confidence responses dominate the result, Neff becomes smaller, indicating greater uncertainty.
Parameter dimension		A broad category used to group similar MSFD reporting parameters or EV measurements. For example, parameters such as density, number of individuals and counts are grouped under abundance; parameters such as range, area, cover and spatial extent are grouped under distribution/extent.
Variable		A broad property of the ecosystem, ocean, habitat or species that is monitored through observations. In this report, EVs are treated as monitoring variables that define the type of information needed, such as species abundance, habitat extent, biomass, oxygen, nutrients or seagrass cover and composition.
Parameter		A specific measurement or metric reported to quantify a variable. In WISEMARINE, parameters refer to the reported measurements used by Member States to inform MSFD criteria. For example, an abundance-related variable may be reported using parameters such as counts, density, number of individuals per unit area or biomass.
Indicator		An indicator consists of one or several parameters chosen to represent or “indicate” a specific situation, condition or aspect of the marine environment, and to simplify a complex reality (GES4SEAS Deliverable 2.0). In MSFD assessments, indicators are used to interpret monitoring information in relation to criteria, environmental status, trends or progress towards Good Environmental Status.

